

Manifold learning for image-based digital twinning in mechanics of materials

I) Provider description

Centre des Matériaux at Mines Paris PSL University is working on material science for energy, transportation and health applications. Many digital images of materials at various scales are involved. On these images we observe defects and anomalies. Some are acceptable, but not all. A digital twinning of materials, as they are observed on digital images, enable to develop a scientific understanding of defect harmfulness. Today, mechanics of materials is assisted by Artificial Intelligence to transfer our modeling work-flow to real time applications. Tolerating defects in materials avoids wasting raw materials and the energy used to transform them.

II) Contact

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III) Problem definition

The aim of the Data Challenge is to predict an image of mechanical fields around defects from the image of these defects. It is a regression task by using supervised machine learning. Each prediction must also generate a coordinate of the input defect in a latent space of reduced dimension. Such a latent space can be further used for model order reduction in mechanics of materials, data interpolation, clustering... But the exploitation of the latent space is not in the scope the Data Challenge. Here, the smaller the dimension of the latent space for a given prediction accuracy, the better.

The defect images have been obtained from X-ray tomography of welded assemblies.

The database contains 4,000 2D defect images and mechanical predictions around these defects (Cauchy strains and stresses). The mechanical predictions were produced by numerical twins in continuum mechanics. However, image-based digital twinning takes a long time to set up. This makes it incompatible with in-process diagnosis of welded joints. Machine learning predictions therefore make it possible to diagnose the harmfulness of defects in the context of Industry 4.0.

IV) Data description

We consider voids in additive manufacturing. The defect images have been obtained from the X-ray tomography of welded joints. *The database contains 4,000 2D defect images and related mechanical predictions around these defects (the components of the strain tensor). The mechanical predictions were produced by digital twins in continuum mechanics, assuming linear elasticity around the voids. The digital twin has been submitted to 3 mechanical loads: 2 macroscopic tension and one macroscopic shear. Each load generates a strain field with 3 scalar components (2 elongations and one shear strain). Here, a mechanical field is a tensor of data similar to digital image. The mechanical load is kept fixed for all defect instances.*

Input x: gray-scale image of size 48 x 48

Output y: tensor of size 48 x 48 x 3 x 3, where $y[i,j,i_comp,i_load]$ is the stress component i_comp for mechanical load i_load at pixel $[i,j]$.

The data set contains 4000 samples.

V) Metric

We use the MSE metric to quantify error between a participant submission and the true output y, but this MSE is weighted by the dimension of the latent space:

$$\text{Metric} = (1+N)^3 \text{MSE},$$

where the weight N^3 accounts for the computational complexity of further exploitation of the latent space.

VI) Benchmark

A simple architecture with convolutional layers is proposed to obtain first prediction result. This architecture is similar to an auto-encoder, where the encoder generates the latent coordinates of the input image and the decoder generates the output mechanical field from the latent coordinates. When changing this architecture make sure to evaluate the right dimension of the latent space, which is the dimension of all data that predict the encoder.